

**FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE PHILOSOPHICAL AND SYNERGETIC
FOUNDATIONS OF GLOBALIZATION**

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Abstract: This article provides a scientific analysis of the philosophical and synergetic foundations of the globalization process. The socio-historical formation of globalization, its role in civilizational development, and its significance in the development of modern society are demonstrated. Furthermore, the process of globalization is considered based on a synergetic approach, revealing its features of systemicity, uncertainty, openness, and self-organization. The article analyzes the interaction of factors such as cultural integration, information exchange, and economic cooperation in the process of globalization from a philosophical perspective. The research findings indicate the necessity of studying the process of globalization not merely as an economic or political phenomenon, but as a complex socio-philosophical system. It is also emphasized that the synergetic approach serves as an important theoretical basis for understanding the dynamic features of the globalization process.

Keywords: globalization, philosophy, synergetics, social system, self-organization, civilizational development, sustainable development, integration.

Introduction: The development of the modern world is closely linked to the process of globalization. Since the second half of the 20th century, globalization has become one of the main trends in the development of the world community. As a result of the development of information and communication technologies, the expansion of international economic relations, and the strengthening of cultural and civilizational dialogue, humanity operates in a single global space. Globalization is not merely an economic or political process, but a complex social phenomenon with deep philosophical and civilizational content. It affects all spheres of society—economy, politics, culture, science, and technology. Therefore, philosophical and methodological approaches are of great importance in the scientific analysis of the globalization process. From a philosophical perspective, globalization represents a specific stage of human development. It forms the relationship between national and universal values and creates a new civilizational space. At the same time, globalization brings to the agenda issues such as the preservation of cultural diversity and the strengthening of national identity. The purpose of the article is to analyze the philosophical and synergetic foundations of the globalization process and to reveal the patterns of its formation and development.

Analysis of literature on the topic. The works of renowned scholars such as N. Berdyaev, M. Korpenko, N. Knyazeva, S. Otamurodov, and M. Abdullaeva, as well as the literature on the topic of changes and consequences of human spirituality in the context of globalization, primarily highlight the impact of global integration processes on personal and social values, the harmony of national and universal human culture, and the problems of spiritual and moral crisis. The research analyzes the philosophical views of Western and Eastern scholars, sociological observations, and spiritual transformations in modern society, and evaluates their positive and negative consequences on a scientific basis.

Research methodology. In presenting the article, methods of dialectical, systematic analysis, synergetic approach, historical-philosophical, comparative, and comprehensive approaches were used.

Results and discussion. From a philosophical perspective, globalization manifests as a natural and legitimate stage of human development. It is inextricably linked to the dialectical laws of social development. From a dialectical perspective, any social process develops on the basis of the unity and struggle of opposites. Globalization is also formed as a result of the interaction between national and universal interests, traditions and innovations, and local and global trends. In our view, one should look at the history of technology before predicting the future of globalization. In this regard, according to K.J. Tulenova: "Scientific forecasts are assumptions about unknown events of the past and present (objects, processes, laws, facts, etc.), as well as about future events, which are put forward as conclusions based on popular theories, laws, and hypotheses." [1]

From an ontological perspective, globalization is viewed as an objective process uniting all of humanity into a single social system. This process is linked to the expansion of humanity's economic, political, and cultural ties.

From an epistemological perspective, globalization leads to the global dissemination of knowledge and information. The Internet and digital technologies have expanded human learning opportunities, shaping a global information space. Views on the existence of positive and negative aspects of globalization are described. Habibuli Hana Hongira, who studied aspects of globalization, says: Globalization is a process that leads to victories and losses. Some see globalization as a train that destroys everything in its path, while others see it as a source of benefits that leads to economic growth and modernization. [2]

We can see that such an approach to globalization has a complex nature of research, and it is contradictory to approach it at once. According to the ideologist of globalization M. Waters, "In the world of globalization, a new world is being formed independent of territorial borders, political and economic relations between countries, and national interests." [3] The established world represents a single society, a single culture. This means the voluntary integration of cultures into human culture." From an axiological perspective, globalization serves the formation of universal human values. However, at the same time, the issue of preserving national culture and traditions is of great importance.

Synergetics, as a science that studies the patterns of self-organization of complex systems, serves as a vital theoretical framework for understanding the process of globalization. Social systems, like systems in nature, are dynamic and nonlinear. In the process of globalization, states, cultures, and economic systems interact, shaping new social orders. According to the synergetic perspective, social systems reach bifurcation points in certain situations. At these points, the future direction of the system's development is selected. In the process of globalization, economic crises, technological revolutions, and political changes also manifest as such bifurcation points. Another important feature of synergetics is the process of self-organization. In the context of globalization, the world economy, international organizations, and cultural relations are formed to a certain extent based on internal laws.

The history of globalization is conventionally divided into several stages: The first stage of trade relations—economic and cultural ties between ancient civilizations; The stage of industrial globalization is the expansion of international economic relations as a result of the industrial revolution; The stage of information globalization is the development of information technologies and the Internet; The stage of digital globalization is the rapid development of artificial intelligence, the digital economy, and innovative technologies. [4] At the current stage, globalization is shaping a new economic and cultural space on a global scale. The research findings demonstrate the necessity of applying philosophical and synergetic approaches together to gain a deeper understanding of the globalization process. While philosophical analysis reveals the general patterns of globalization, the synergetic approach allows for the explanation of its

dynamic and complex characteristics.[5] The combination of these two approaches serves as an important theoretical basis for forecasting the future development trends of the globalization process.

Conclusions and suggestions. Firstly, globalization is an important stage in human development, and its philosophical and synergetic foundations are manifested through the interaction of social systems, self-organization, and cooperation between civilizations.

Secondly, while philosophical analysis reveals the essence of the globalization process, the synergetic approach explains its dynamic and non-linear characteristics, helping to understand complex social processes in global development.

Thirdly, in the context of globalization, maintaining a balance between national and universal values is of great importance, as this process ensures the stability of societal development and cultural diversity.

Fourth, the synergetic approach interprets globalization as an open and complex system, allowing for an understanding of issues of self-organization, bifurcation points, and stability in social processes.

Fifth, the study of the philosophical and synergetic foundations of globalization serves to understand the prospects for the development of world civilization, develop sustainable development strategies, and solve global problems.

To study this topic and apply it in practice, the following practical we propose:

- In order to gain a deeper understanding of globalization processes, it is advisable to introduce special courses on philosophy and synergetics in higher education institutions, as well as to develop systemic and global thinking in students.

- It is necessary to establish scientific centers in research institutions that study globalization processes from a philosophical and synergetic perspective, as well as to expand international scientific cooperation.

- To effectively participate in the global information space while preserving national culture and values, it is necessary to develop skills in intercultural communication and global thinking within the education system.

It is important to ensure stability in social systems and enhance adaptability to global changes by utilizing a synergistic approach in the development of state and social development strategies.

- In the context of globalization, it is advisable to further develop international integration in the fields of science, education, and the economy through the effective use of innovative technologies and digital communications.

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